

Direct-To-Object, or DTO printing, is a distinctive form of digital printing that involves using ultraviolet (UV) light to cure or dry the ink almost as soon as it is applied to a prepared substrate. Unique UV printing is possible. The substrate can include flat objects and any domed or cylindrical objects. This can consist of almost all metals, acrylic, plastic, glass, canvas, and even wood. After the UV ink has been applied to the substrate, the special ultraviolet lights in the printer immediately apply the ink to the material, drying it, and adhering it to the substrate.

Initially, the UV printing process was developed for gel nail varnishes. The gel polish is then applied to the nails using a UV light. This results in a flawless manicure that is quick drying, durable, and long-lasting. However, eventually, the benefits of using ultraviolet light began to be recognized and started being used in industrial and commercial markets. This forms the foundation of UV printing services and the associated printing industry. It is now used to create flyers, leaflets, signs, screen printing, and even bottle labels, just a few examples. UV printing is not unlike traditional printing. But the inks used as well the drying and curing methods are different. This is due to the unique nature of the printing technology.

Traditional printing uses solvent inks that are applied to a substrate and heated to cure it. Solvent-based inks can evaporate, spread out onto the surface of the substrate before they are dried, and release volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Unpleasant odor is produced by the heat used to cure solvent ink to substrate. Furthermore, the solvent inks are absorbed into the substrate, which can result in faded colors. Spray powders also make it difficult to dry the ink and prevent it from offsetting. This can cause the entire process to take several days. Due to the nature of the printing press, traditional printing can only be done on paper and other similar materials. It can't be used on metal, plastic, glass or acrylic.

Specialized UV inks can be used for UV printing. Instead of heat, high-intensity LED ultraviolet lights are used to cure the ink onto the medium that it is printed on. The ultraviolet light follows closely behind the ink as it is distributed onto the substrate. The ink will dry immediately regardless of the substrate. The ink does not evaporate because it dries quickly. Therefore, it can't spread onto the material that it is printed on.

In addition to the quick-drying capabilities and the eco-friendliness of UV printing, this ultraviolet printing method and the associated form of ink transfer can also be used with various materials, including paper, plastic, foil, acrylic, foam, etc. There are no VOCs or ozone emissions into the atmosphere. This feature will interest companies that prize sustainability in their printing processes.

Imagine the possibilities when you consider digitally printing directly to the item instead of printing on a sticker and then needing to place the sticker on the object. DTO Direct-To-Object allows you to print in full color directly on the item.